

A Study of Students' Absenteeism in Higher Education of a Tribal Area of Maharashtra

Nandkishor J. Suryawanshi

Arts, Science and Commerce College, Chikhaldara, Maharashtra, India (444805)

Corresponding author- **Nandkishor J. Suryawanshi**

Email- njsascc@gmail.com

Abstract

One of the problems that the majority of higher education institutions (HEIs) face today is student attendance. Many colleges and universities have policies requiring students to attend class. In higher education system, it is believed that attendance has a favorable impact on academic success, notwithstanding the various restrictions. One of the causes of academic failure is considered to be absenteeism from class lectures. Being physically present for class does not constitute being actively engaged in the work and activities of the class. Absences may be authorized, unauthorized or caused by extenuating circumstances. In this present study, an attempt has been made to identify the factors which cause students' absenteeism in a higher education institute of a tribal area. In order to do this, a survey was conducted using a questionnaire.

Keywords

Students' absenteeism, higher education, tribal area

Introduction

The attitude of students skipping courses has spread throughout higher education and is a big source of worry higher education institutes. It has been determined that such absences have detrimental effects on both students and the institutes. Academic performance is a measure of how well a student or institution has met its educational objectives. It is frequently assessed by testing or ongoing evaluation. Learning achievement preceded consistent attendance in class. Students must be in class regularly in order to profit from the educational programme. Fewer opportunities exist for irregular students to study. As a result, their academic potential is limited. Therefore, regular attendance in class is given top attention. When students miss class, they lose out on important learning and the advantages of the specific examples that teachers employ to simplify complex ideas. Student absenteeism can be attributed to a variety of circumstances. In practically all Indian institutions and colleges, attendance of 75% is required; failing to do so might result in a student receiving a failing mark or even failure.

Review of Literature

Tripathi Archana (2022) carried out a study to examine the factors which are responsible for students' absenteeism in higher education in the district of Champawat in Uttarakhand. The factors identified were lack of desire and motivation, availability of substandard material in the market, defected and wrongful evaluation system etc. Lukkarinen Anna, Paula Koivukangas and Seppala Tomi (2016) in their investigation showed the relationship between class attendance and student performance. Ancheta Ruel F., Daniel Deny and Ahmad Reshma (2021) explained the effect of class attendance on academic performance of students. Khanal Shanti Prasad (2019) examined the irregular

attendance of university students at class and its relation to their academic achievement. He formulated a hypothesis that there is significance relationship between attendance of the students of the class and their academic performance. Kousalya P., Ravindranath V., and Vizayakumar K. (2006) in their study illustrated the application of analytical hierarchy process (AHP) in the context of student absenteeism in engineering colleges. Clores Michael A. (2009) in his qualitative research study on school absenteeism among college students discussed pedagogical, psychological and socio-cultural implications based on the findings. Srivastava Meenakshi(2018) conducted a study to identify factors that cause students discontent with the classroom learning environment. Lucey Siobhan and Grydaki Maria (2022) examined the effect of implementing an incentive scheme on seminar and performance. Khan Mohammed Shamim(2021) conducted a research to investigate the causes and remedies of students absentee. The identified major factors responsible for students' absenteeism were as students' financial crisis, distant residence, unsafe public transport, sometimes teacher absenteeism and a lacking in the education policy. Muir Jenny (2009) in the research showed that tendency for students who attend classes more regularly to gain better marks, especially if they are weaker or if they have the potential for a top mark, although it is not clear cut. Akkus Murat and Cinkir Sakir (2022) evaluated the status of student absenteeism, its impacts on educational environments and the relevant policies available.

Aim of Study

Arts, Science and Commerce College, Chikhaldara run by Sipna Shikshan Prasarak Mandal, Amravati, was established in the year 1996 with the aim of achieving holistic development of the people of Melghat, a remote, hilly and tribal area

of Maharashtra. The vast area of Melghat is about 4000 sq. km. formed mainly by two talukas Chikhaldara and Dharni, partly Anjangaon Surji and Achalpur talukas of Amravati district and partly Akot taluka of Akola district. The area is predominantly tribal and educationally as well as economically backward. The main social problems here are superstition, unemployment, malnutrition, migration, educational dropout etc. It is very important to increase the GER of this area in overcoming such problems. Most of the students in the college come from this area. Absenteeism can cause their academic performance. In today's higher education, student involvement and attendance in class are crucial factors. Class attendance has been found to be a significant predictor of academic results in several earlier studies: Attending more classes, results in better final grades for students. For this, it was proposed to carry out a systematic study to identify the factors causing students' absenteeism.

Study Objective

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Students enrolled in college and participating in the survey

The total number of students enrolled in the science stream is 238 out of which 222 (93.27%) students have participated in the survey.

Main means of household income

Out of total 222 respondents 112 (50.45%) of the respondents has agriculture as their main source of family income. There are 26 (11.71%) students who said that the main source of family income is government job. While 64(28.82%) students responded that daily wage is the main

source of their income of the family. 13 (5.75%) students indicated that the primary source of family income is a private job. From this we can see that the main source of income for most of the students' families is agriculture and daily labor.

Willingness to pursue higher education

221 (99.54%) students wanted to pursue higher education while only 1 (0.45%) didn't want to pursue higher education. This demonstrates that

the number of students who want to pursue higher education is large while the number of students who do not want to pursue higher education is negligible.

Students' college attendance

When trying to know the attendance of the students in the college, 114 (51.35%) students expressed that they come regularly to the college while 108(48.65 %) students expressed that they are

irregular. This shows that the percent of regular students is slightly higher than the irregular students.

Reasons for absenteeism in college

On knowing the reasons for this, 39(36.11%) students remain absent due to poor economic conditions. 07(6.48%) students remain absent due to not getting admission in the hostel. 23(21.29%) students are absent due to family

responsibilities. 03(2.77%) students remain absent due to ill health. 29(26.85%) students are absent due to transportation (accessibility) problem, 07(6.48%) students are absent due to lack of accommodation

Willingness to do part-time job

Are the students willing to do employment if they get part time employment? Knowing this, 167 (75.22%) students were willing to do this job

while unwilling to employ, the number was 55 (24.77%).

If provided part-time employment opportunity then ready to attend the college regularly

169(76.12%) students expressed their reaction that they will attend college regularly if part-time employment is provided to them in Chikhaldara and nearby areas.

Fields of employment and student's choice

Many students mentioned their interest to do part time jobs. Considering the field of temporary employment opportunities available in Chikhaldara and trying to know in which field the students want to do part time job, 157(70.72%) means most of the students were interested to work in government/semi-government offices The number

of those who were willing to work in hotels, resorts was 26(11.71%) The number of students willing to work in construction field was 19 (12.05%). The number of students who were willing to work in different shops, private offices, NGOs etc. was 13(5.85%). The number of students who didn't express any kind of reaction is 7(3.15%).

Opinion about college

155(69.81%) students responded that the college is excellent/ very good when their opinions were asked about the college. The number of students who did not express any opinion about the college is 53(23.87%). While expressing their opinions in this context, the teachers in the college are good, the college has many facilities for students and the college premises are good.

Conclusion

On the basis of striking findings from this research, the conclusive remarks may be expressed in the following way.

Agriculture and daily wage labor is the main source of income for most of the students' families. 99.54% of students desire to pursue higher education. Percent of regular students is slightly higher than the irregular students. Financial situation, daily work and family responsibilities, lack of transportation are the major reasons for student absenteeism in college.75.22% of the admitted students are willing to take up employment. In the field of employment, most 70 % students preferred part-time employment in government and semi-government offices. Majority of the students expressed their opinion that the college is excellent/ very good and the teachers, staff and facilities of the college are also very good.

Acknowledgement

I wish to acknowledge the Management and Principal of our college for providing the opportunity to undertake the study and their valuable suggestions for this. Thanks are also due to my colleagues for their support.

References

1. Tripathi Archana, A Study About Factors Causing The Absenteeism of Students In Higher Education of Uttarakhand, International Journal of Creative Research, Vol.10(1), 2022, 974-983.
2. Lukkarinen Anna, Paula Koivukangas and Seppala Tomi, Relationship between Class Attendance and Student Performance, Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, 228, 2016, 341- 347.
3. Ancheta Ruel F., Daniel Deny and Ahmad Reshma, Effect of Class Attendance on Academic Performance, European Journal of Education Studies, Vol. 8(9), 2011, 115-131.
4. Khanal Shanti Prasad, Irregular Attendance of University Students at Class and Its Relation to Their Academic Achievement, Tribhuvan University Journal, Vol. 33(1), 115-128.
5. Kousalya P., Ravindranath V. and Vizayakumar K., Student Absenteeism in Engineering Colleges: Evaluation of Alternatives Using AHP, Journal of Applied Mathematics and Decision Sciences, Vol. 2006, Art.ID, 58232, 1-26.
6. Clores Michael A., A Qualitative Research Study on School Absenteeism among College Students, The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher, Vol.18(2), 2009, 151-165.
7. Srivastava Meenakshi, A Study of Absenteeism in Context of Student's Discontent with the Classrooms Learning Environment, International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts, Vol. 6(2), 2018, 1096-1106.
8. Lucey Siobhan and Grydaki Maria, University Attendance and Academic Performance: Encouraging Student Engagement, Scottish

- Journal of Political Economy, Vol.70, 2023, 180-199.
9. Khan Mohammed Shamim, Investigation on Absenteeism among Undergraduate Students: A Study at a Government College in Bangladesh, International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods, 9(2), 2021, 940-952.
 10. Muir Jenny, Student Attendance: Is It Important and What Do Students Think?, CEBE Transactions, Vol. 6(2), 2009, 50-69.
 11. Akkus Murat and Cinkir Sakir, International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies, Vol. 9(Special Issue), 2022, 978-997.